

Structure-Dependent Electrical Double Layer Capacitances of the Basal Plane Pd(hkl) Electrodes in HClO₄

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ABSTRACT

Electrical double layer capacitance (C_{DL}) measurements are among the key experiments in physical electrochemistry to understand the properties of electrified solid/liquid interfaces. C_{DL} serves as a critical parameter for developing physical models of electrochemical interfaces. Palladium (Pd) electrodes are among the most widely used functional materials in many applications, including (electro)catalysis. In this work, we report double layer capacitances of the basal plane Pd(111), Pd(100), and Pd(110) electrodes in aqueous $HClO_4$ electrolytes measured using electrochemical impedance spectroscopy. Importantly, we find that the C_{DL} values estimated at the minima of the capacitance vs. electrode potential curves can be correlated with the DFT-calculated adsorption energies for water molecules and the coordination of electrode surface atoms. Our results thus suggest that it might be possible to find simple descriptors of the electrical double layer (EDL) analogously to those used for functional electrode materials. Taken together, such descriptors could be employed for efficient high-throughput screening of various electrode/electrolyte interfaces, such as in supercapacitor and electrocatalytic systems.

INTRODUCTION

The knowledge of basic parameters characterizing the electrified solid/liquid interface is of great importance to understanding its functionality, such as catalytic properties [1,2,3,4,5,6]. The capacitance of the electric double layer (C_{DL}) is one of those critical parameters [7]. For example, the position of the C_{DL} minima is often associated with the so-called potential of zero charge or maximum entropy, indicating which electrolyte compositions are beneficial for promoting electrocatalytic reactions [8,9,10,11,12,13,14]. However, despite their importance, the C_{DL} values of model single crystal electrodes are available only for a relatively small amount of systems (see, *e.g.* [15,16,17]). This can be partly explained by the challenges in preparing single crystal electrodes and fundamental issues related to the measurements, for example, due to the so-called frequency dispersion of the double layer capacitance [18,19,20], even for flat single crystal electrodes in electrolytes, which do not contain specifically adsorbing ions.

Palladium (Pd) is a versatile material with a wide range of applications. In electrocatalysis, it is considered among the so-called energy materials, catalyzing the hydrogen evolution, hydrogen oxidation, and oxygen reduction reactions [21]. In this work, we report the double layer capacitances of the basal plane Pd(hkl) single crystal electrodes, namely, Pd(111), Pd(100), and Pd(110) surfaces. The utilized electrolyte is 0.1M HClO₄, a standard medium used in multiple electrocatalytic and other physico-chemical applications. Furthermore, we establish the hypothesis on the intrinsic correlations between the energetic adsorption characteristics of electrolyte components, the structure of the Pd(hkl) surfaces, and the double layer capacitance found close to the potential of zero charge (PZC). We suggest that these correlations can be used to improve or supplement the rational design of new materials for various energy conversion and storage applications.

EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

The Pd(111), Pd(100), and Pd(110) disk electrodes (\varnothing : 5 mm, 99.999%, MaTecK, Jülich, Germany) were oriented more precisely than 0.05° and polished to a nominal roughness of less than 30nm. Before the cyclic voltammetric (CV) and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) experiments, the crystals were annealed for 2h in Ar (5.0, Westfalen, Germany) atmosphere at 950°C in a furnace (Heraeus Instruments RO 7/50, Germany), cooled down overnight, and transferred into a standard three-electrode cell. To avoid an oxidation during the transportation by exposing the sample to the air, the electrode surface was protected by a droplet of ultra-pure water (Evoqua Milli-Q[®], 18.2 M Ω cm). Electrochemical scanning tunneling microscopy (EC-STM) imaging was performed under potential control (0.0V vs. platinum) to prevent electrochemical surface reactions. In all experiments, 0.1M HClO₄ (Suprapur[®], Merck, Germany) was used as an electrolyte. The measurements were performed using a VSP-300 potentiostat (BioLogic, France).

Electrochemical Voltammetric and Impedance Measurements

All glassware and Teflon cell parts were cleaned in a piranha solution, a 1:2 mixture of 30% H₂O₂ (Suprapur[®], Merck, Germany) and 96% H₂SO₄ (Suprapur[®], Merck, Germany), and treated/washed with boiling ultrapure Milli-Q[®] water with a resistivity of 18.2 M Ω ·cm before the experiments. The standard three-electrode configuration cell was operated with a mercury-mercurous sulfate electrode (MMS) (SI Analytics, Germany) and Pd-wire (\varnothing 0.25 mm, 99.95%, MaTecK, Germany) as the reference counter, respectively. A starting potential of 0.57 V_{RHE} was used to avoid possible electrochemical surface processes before the actual measurement started. The quality of the annealed single crystalline surface was verified by cyclic voltammetry (CVs) in Ar-saturated 0.1M HClO₄ at a potential range between 0.2 and 1.2V_{RHE} and a scan rate of 50 mV s⁻¹.

The electrochemical impedance spectroscopy measurements were performed within a frequency range between 50kHz and 1Hz using a perturbation amplitude of 10mV. To suppress possible potentiostat- and reference electrode-related artifacts, a shunt capacitor was connected between the reference and a dummy electrode. The dummy electrode was placed close to the Luggin capillary. For the EIS data analysis, the housemade software “EIS Spectrum Analyzer 1.3” was used [22,23]. The quality of the recorded spectra was ensured by a Krammer-Kroenig check.

Electrochemical Scanning Tunneling Microscopy

Electrochemical scanning tunneling microscopy (EC-STM) imaging was performed using a Nanoscope III SPM Multimode (Veeco Instruments), connected to a Veeco Nanoscope Universal bipotentiostat and a Nanoscope IIID controller in 0.1M HClO₄. For all EC-STM measurements, the single crystals were clamped between a stainless steel plate and a TeflonTM ring acting as the case of the miniature electrochemical cell. A Pt wire (Ø 0.5 mm, 99.99%, MaTecK, Germany) was used as a quasi-reference electrode and a curled Pd wire (Ø 0.25 mm, 99.95%, MaTecK, Germany) as the counter electrode. The STM-tips were mechanically cut from a Pt/Ir wire (Pt80/Ir20, Ø 0.25, Goodfellow GmbH) and insulated by Apiezon wax. Detailed information on this technique can be found in [24,25,26,27]. The visualization of the EC-STM data was implemented by using WSxM 5.0 Develop 9.4 [28].

Computational Approach

The atomic structures of the Pd surfaces with converged computational parameters were taken from the Materials Project [29] and used for adsorption calculations.

Ab initio simulations were performed using the density-functional-theory (DFT) plane-wave VASP code [30,31,32,33]. The revised Perdew-Burke-Ernzerhof (RPBE) exchange-correlation functional [34] together with the PAW Pd, O, and H potentials [35] were employed. The D3 approach within Grimme's formalism was used to correct for non-local van der Waals interactions [36,37]. Cutoff energy of 520eV was employed in all calculations. The structures were optimized until the total energies, and atomic forces were converged to within 10^{-5} eV and 0.03eV/Å, respectively. The (100), (110), and (111) surfaces of Pd were modeled using the periodic slabs consisting of eight, eight, and ten atomic layers, respectively, taken from the Materials Project [38]. The dimensions of the cells employed to estimate the adsorption energies for H₂O, H, and OH species were 8.38x8.38Å², 8.38x11.86Å², and 8.38x8.38Å² with at least 13Å vacuum gap. The Monkhorst-Pack *k*-point mesh of 5x5x1 was used in all slab calculations. The adsorption energies were computed considering water, proton, and hydroxyl species as adsorbates. All calculations were performed for charge-neutral supercells. The negative adsorption energies correspond to attractive interactions between the adsorbate and the metal surface.

All potentials presented in this work for CV, EIS data, and DFT calculations have been referred to versus the reversible hydrogen electrode (RHE).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 1 summarizes the results of voltammetric and EC-STM characterization of the Pd(111), Pd(100), and Pd(110) electrodes. The samples demonstrate typical CV-profiles (**Figures 1A-C**) [39,40] with: (i) the underpotential deposition of hydrogen region between *ca.* 0.2 and 0.5V, (ii) the double layer region, and (iii) the region of adsorption of the oxygenated species at the

electrode potentials more positive than *ca.* 0.6V. The corresponding EC-STM images (**Figures 1D-F**) generally reveal smooth surfaces with atomically flat terraces consisting of thousands of Pd atoms.

Figure 1. (A-C) Typical cyclic voltammograms (first cycles) and (D-F) corresponding EC-STM pictures of freshly annealed (A,D) Pd(111), (B,E) Pd(100) and (C,F) Pd(110) in 0.1M HClO₄. Scanning rate for CVs (A-C): 50 mV s⁻¹.

Figure 2 shows typical examples of the electrochemical impedance spectroscopy data of the investigated palladium electrodes. The equivalent electric circuit (EEC) shown in **Figure 2A** was found to adequately describe the impedance response of the systems within the double layer regions. It consists of two elements, the uncompensated resistance associated with the electrolyte, R_U , and the impedance of the electric double layer, Z_{DL} , given by the formula presented in **Figure 2A**. With the exponent n approaching 1, Z_{DL} is close to the impedance of an ideal capacitance. Therefore, the corresponding parameter C'_{DL} is further considered as the double layer capacitance in this study.

The dependencies C'_{DL} vs. (E_{RHE}) for the three freshly annealed Pd(hkl) electrodes are shown in **Figure 2B** in the potential regions where no significant side electrochemical reactions occur. Typical fitting examples of the admittance spectra to the EEC are shown in **Figures 2C-E**, confirming that the model describes the experimental data pretty well, with the root-mean-square deviations of less than 2%. It is remarkable in **Figure 2B** that the double layer capacitances are drastically different for all three palladium electrodes, considering that they represent examples of very flat model surfaces. In each of the curves in **Figure 2B**, one can identify the C'_{DL} minima, $C_{DL,min}$, at different electrode potentials and with different corresponding capacitance values. These minima should typically be close to the so-called potentials of zero charges (PZCs), where the net charge of the surface approaches zero.

Somewhat surprisingly, even close to the PZC point, the double layer capacitances drastically depend on the basal plane surface structure. While classical and recent [41] theories of the double layer do not consider the nature of the electrode and its structure, the experiments show that the EDL capacitance significantly depends not only on the electrolyte composition but also

on the electrode structure and its chemical composition [2,3]. Therefore, elucidation of the structure-capacitance relations is an essential part of developing more comprehensive theories of the double layer. As $C_{DL,min}$ also plays a significant role in understanding the electrified interface and the electrocatalytic interfacial charge transfer, in the following, we analyze these data in more detail.

Figure 2. Characterization of Pd(hkl) electrodes using electrochemical impedance spectroscopy. (A) Equivalent electric circuit. (B) Dependences of the double layer capacitance on the electrode potential. (C-E) Examples of impedance spectra together with the fitting (solid lines) to the equivalent circuit for (C) Pd(111), (D) Pd(100), and (E) Pd(110) electrodes.

First of all, we hypothesize that $C_{DL,min}$ reflects the intrinsic interactions between the surface and the electrolyte components with minimal influence of the excessive electrode charge. DFT calculations were used to quantify the adsorption energy for the most important strongly interacting species. Three types of species were considered: water molecules, H^+ , and OH^- species. The results of these calculations are summarized in **Figure 3**.

Figure 3. (A-C) Adsorbate configurations (top view) and DFT-calculated binding energies for H₂O, hydroxyl, and H⁺ species at Pd(hkl) surfaces with the corresponding Pd-O and Pd-H bond lengths indicated in the pictures.

It can be seen that H⁺ species are characterized by the strongest adsorption on the top sites of the Pd surfaces, followed by OH⁻ and then H₂O. Moreover, the corresponding Pd-H and Pd-O bond lengths for the H⁺ and OH⁻ adsorbates are almost unaffected by the surface structure (<1%), while for H₂O, the bond length is significantly stronger influenced by the surface structure. Therefore, one can assume that the most critical interacting species for the C_{DL} analysis are water molecules. Further, they are likely to significantly impact the overall thickness of the inner Helmholtz layer in the double layer structure. In turn, this should be reflected by variations of the double layer capacitance for different surfaces.

For the detailed study of this effect, it is essential to parametrize the Pd(hkl) structures to correlate structure-related information with the double layer capacitance. One can do that using the so-called generalized coordination numbers (GCNs) [42,43,44]. GCN is a parameter that can be considered as a simple quantitative measure related to the structure linking it with an electron density function at the surface. Therefore, GCN is a useful descriptor for the affinity of the surface to the electrolyte components. It considers the first and the second nearest neighbors of the accessible adsorption sites and can be calculated using the following equation (1), weighting each first-nearest neighbor atom (*j*) by its conventional coordination number (*cn(j)*) [44]:

$$\text{GCN} = (1+S)^{-1}[\sum \text{cn}(j)/\text{cn}_{\text{max}}] \quad (1)$$

where *S* is the percentage of strain (negative or positive for compressive or tensile strain) and *cn_{max}* is the maximum number of the direct neighbors in the bulk phase, which is defined as 12 on *fcc* and *hcp* crystals, and as 8 for the *bcc* ones (examples of GCN calculations for 111, 100

and 110 palladium surfaces are given in the Supporting Information). By assuming zero strain for the freshly annealed surfaces, one can calculate $\text{GCN}(\text{Pd}_{111}) = 7.5$, $\text{GCN}(\text{Pd}_{100}) = 6.6(6)$, and $\text{GCN}(\text{Pd}_{110}) = 5.85$.

Remarkably, the DFT-calculated binding energies for H_2O molecules scale linearly with the GCNs of the investigated palladium planes (**Figure 4A**), enabling further parametrization of the surfaces in energetic and structural terms simultaneously. In other words, one can use GCNs to characterize and quantify the affinity of the surface toward electrolyte components (in the following, only H_2O is considered) in simple terms.

To correlate the GCN with the $C_{\text{DL},\text{min}}$, consider that the generalized coordination number is a measure of “unsaturated” surface electron density”. One can assume that the higher this value, the lower the densities and the longer the effective distances between the surface atoms and the first layer of water molecules (see, *e.g.*, **Figure 3**). One should also consider the different number of accessible surface sites for the water molecules per unit area, S , for different basal surfaces (see **Figure S1** in Supporting Information). Therefore, it is reasonable to define a new function, F_e , which should be connected to $C_{\text{DL},\text{min}}$ in a first approximation:

$$F_e = S/\sum\text{GCN} \quad (2)$$

Figure 4B reveals an excellent quasi-linear correlation between $C_{\text{DL},\text{min}}$ and F_e , where $C_{\text{DL},\text{min}}$ increases with decreasing $\sum\text{GCN}$, as follows: $\text{Pd}(111) < \text{Pd}(100) < \text{Pd}(110)$.

(A)

(B)

Figure 4. (A) DFT-calculated binding energies for H₂O molecules for different Pd(hkl) surfaces correlated with the GCNs. (B) The double layer capacitances found at the minima of the capacitance/electrode potential curves correlated with the F_e parameter defined via surface area normalized generalized coordination numbers.

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, we carried out EIS, voltammetric, and electrochemical scanning tunneling microscopy characterizations of Pd(111), Pd(100), and Pd(110) electrodes. The EIS measurements revealed a strong surface dependence of the double layer capacitance close to the potential of zero charge, being *ca.* 31.7 μF/cm² for Pt(111), *ca.* 37.7 μF/cm² for Pd(100), and *ca.* 65 μF/cm² for Pd(110). We were also able to correlate the capacitance data with the surface adsorption energies for water species and the generalized coordination numbers of the Pd surfaces. The results of this work thus suggest that it may be possible to characterize the EDL properties such as the double layer capacitance using simple physical descriptors. Further joint

experiment-theory investigations are necessary to generalize the obtained results to other electrochemical systems.

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REFERENCES

1. Lust, E. Electrical Double Layers. Double Layers at Single-crystal and Polycrystalline Electrodes. *Encyclopedia of Electrochemistry* Bard, A. J., Eds., Wiley, **2002**, DOI: 10.1002/9783527610426.bard010204
2. Garlyyev, B.; Xue, S.; Watzele, S.; Scieszka, D.; Bandarenka, A. S. Influence of the Nature of the Alkali Metal Cations on the Electrical Double-Layer Capacitance of Model Pt(111) and Au(111) Electrodes. *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.* **2018**, *9* (8), 1927-1930. DOI: 10.1021/acs.jpcllett.8b00610
3. Xue, S.; Garlyyev, B.; Auer, A.; Kunze-Liebhäuser, J.; Bandarenka, A. S. How the Nature of the Alkali Metal Cations Influences the Double-Layer Capacitance of Cu, Au and Pt Single-Crystal Electrodes. *J. Phys. Chem. C* **2020**, *124*, 12442-12447. DOI: 10.1021/acs.jpcc.0c01715
4. Simon, P.; Gogotsi, Y.; Dunn, B. Where Do Batteries End and Supercapacitors Begin?. *Science* **2014**, *343* (6176), 1210–1211. DOI: 10.1126/science.1249625
5. Kornyshev, A. A. Double-Layer in Ionic Liquids: Paradigm Change?. *J. Phys. Chem. B* **2007**, *111* (20), 5545– 5557. DOI: 10.1021/jp067857o
6. Sebastián-Pascual, P.; Shao-Horn, Y.; Escudero-Escribano, M. Toward Understanding the Role of the Electric Double Layer Structure and Electrolyte Effects on Well-Defined Interfaces for Electrocatalysis. *Curr. Opin. Electrochem.* **2022**, *32*, 100918. DOI: 10.1016/j.coelec.2021.100918
7. Haid, R. W.; Ding X.; Sarpey, T. K.; Bandarenka, A. S.; Garlyyev B. Exploration of the Electrical Double-Layer Structure: Influence of Electrolyte Components on the Double-Layer Capacitance and Potential of Maximum Entropy. *Curr. Opin. Electrochem.* **2022**, *32*, 100882. DOI: 10.1016/j.coelec.2021.100882
8. Ledezma-Yanez, I.; Wallace, W. D. Z.; Sebastián-Pascual, P.; Climent, V.; Feliu, J. M.; Koper, M. T. M. Interfacial Water Reorganization as a pH-dependent Descriptor of the

-
- Hydrogen Evolution Rate on Platinum Electrodes. *Nat. Energy* **2017**, *2*, 17031. DOI: 10.1038/NENERGY.2017.31
9. Ding X.; Scieszka, D.; Watzele, S.; Xue, S.; Garlyyev, B.; Haid, R. W.; Bandarenka, A. S. A Systematic Study of the Influence of Electrolyte Ions on the Electrode Activity. *ChemElectroChem* **2022**, *9* (1), e202101088. DOI: 10.1002/celec.202101088
10. Deng, B.; Huang, M.; Zhao, X.; Mou, S.; Dong, F. Interfacial Electrolyte Effects on Electrocatalytic CO₂ Reduction. *ACS Catal.* **2022**, *12* (1), 331-362. DOI: 10.1021/acscatal.1c03501
11. Huang, B.; Rao, R.R.; You, S.; Myint, K.H.; Song Y.; Wang Y.; Ding, W.; Giordano, L.; Zhang, Y.; Wang, T.; Muy, S.; Katayama, Y.; Grossman, J. C.; Willard, A. P.; Xu, K.; Jiang, Y.; Shao-Horn, Y. Cation- and pH-Dependent Hydrogen Evolution and Oxidation Reaction Kinetics. *JACS Au* **2021**, *1* (10), 1674-1687. DOI: 10.1021/jacsau.1c00281
12. Kelly, S. R.; Kirk, Ch.; Chan, K.; Nørskov, J. K. Electric Field Effects in Oxygen Reduction Kinetics: Rationalizing pH Dependence at the Pt(111), Au(111), and Au(100) Electrodes. *J. Phys. Chem. C* **2020**, *124* (27), 14581-14591. DOI: 10.1021/acs.jpcc.0c02127
13. Kelly, S. R.; Heenen, H.H.; Govindarajan, N.; Chan, K.; Nørskov J. K. OH Binding Energy as a Universal Descriptor of the Potential of Zero Charge on Transition Metal Surfaces. *J. Phys. Chem. C* **2022**, *126*, 5521-5528. DOI: 10.26434/chemrxiv-2021-dkb61
14. Li, J.; Stenlid, J. H.; Ludwig, T.; Lamoureux, P. S.; Abild-Pedersen F. Modeling Potential-Dependent Electrochemical Activation Barriers: Revisiting the Alkaline Hydrogen Evolution Reaction. *JACS* **2021**, *143* (46), 19341-19355. DOI: 10.1021/jacs.1c07276
15. Sadkowski, A.; Mothe, A. J.; Neves, R. S. Characterisation of Au(111) and Au(210)/Aqueous Solution Interfaces by Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy. *J. Electroanal. Chem.* **1998**, *455* (1-2), 107-119. DOI: 10.1016/S0022-0728(98)00237-X

-
16. Pajkossy, T.; Kolb, D. M. Anion-Adsorption-Related Frequency-Dependent Double Layer Capacitance of the Platinum-Group Metals in the Double Layer Region. *Electrochim. Acta* **2008**, *53* (25), 7403-7409. DOI: 10.1016/j.electacta.2007.11.068
17. Schouten, K. J. P.; van der Niet, M. J. T. C.; Koper, M. T. M. Impedance Spectroscopy of H and OH Adsorption on Stepped Single-Crystal Platinum Electrodes in Alkaline and Acidic Media. *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **2010**, *12* (46), 15217-15224. DOI: 10.1039/c0cp00104j
18. Lasia, A. The Origin of the Constant Phase Element. *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.* **2022**, *13* (2), 580–589. DOI: 10.1021/acs.jpcllett.1c03782
19. Bandarenka, A. S. Exploring the Interfaces Between Metal Electrodes and Aqueous Electrolytes with Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy. *Analyst* **2013**, *138*, 5540-5554. DOI: 10.1039/C3AN00791J
20. Tymoczko, J.; Colic, V.; Bandarenka, A. S.; Schuhmann, W. Detection of 2D Phase Transitions at the Electrode/Electrolyte Interface Using Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy. *Surf. Sci.* **2015**, *631*, 81-87. DOI: 10.1016/j.susc.2014.04.014
21. Kucernak, A. R. J.; Fahy, K. F.; Naranammalpuram Sundaram V. N. Facile Synthesis of Palladium Phosphide Electrocatalysts and Their Activity for the Hydrogen Oxidation, Hydrogen Evolutions, Oxygen Reduction and Formic Acid Oxidation Reactions. *Catal. Today* **2016**, *262*, 48-56. DOI: 10.1016/j.cattod.2015.09.031
22. Bondarenko, A. S. Analysis of Large Experimental Datasets in Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy. *Anal. Chim. Acta* **2012**, *743*, 41-50. DOI: 10.1016/j.aca.2012.06.055
23. Bandarenka, A.S. Development of hybrid algorithms for EIS data fitting, a book chapter in: *Lecture Notes on Impedance Spectroscopy. Measurement, Modeling and Applications*, Volume 4 / Ed. Kanoun, O. -CRC Press, Taylor and Francis Group, London, **2013**, pp. 29-36
24. Binnig, G.; Rohrer, H. Scanning Tunneling Microscopy - from Birth to Adolescence. *Rev. Mod. Phys.* **1987**, *59* (3), 615-625. DOI: 10.1103/RevModPhys.59.615

-
25. Pfisterer, J. H.; Liang, Y.; Schneider, O.; Bandarenka, A. S. Direct Instrumental Identification of Catalytically Active Surface Sites. *Nature* **2017**, *549* (7670), 74-77. DOI: 10.1038/nature23661
26. Haid, R. W.; Kluge, R. M.; Liang, Y.; Bandarenka, A. S. In Situ Quantification of the Local Electrocatalytic Activity via Electrochemical Scanning Tunneling Microscopy. *Small Methods* **2021**, *5* (2), 2000710. DOI: 10.1002/smt.202000710
27. Haid, R. W.; Kluge, R. M.; Schmidt, T. O.; Bandarenka, A. S. In-situ Detection of Active Sites for Carbon-based Bifunctional Oxygen Reduction and Evolution Catalysis. *Electrochim. Acta* **2021**, *382*, 138285. DOI: 10.1016/j.electacta.2021.138285
28. Horcas, I.; Fernández, R.; Gomez-Rodriguez, J.; Colchero, J.; Gómez-Herrero, J.; Baro, A. WSXM: A Software for Scanning Probe Microscopy and a Tool for Nanotechnology. *Rev. Sci. Instrum.* **2007**, *78* (1), 013705. DOI: 10.1063/1.2432410
29. Jain, A.; Ong, S. P.; Hautier, G.; Chen, W.; Richards, W. D.; Dacek, S.; Cholia, S.; Gunter, D.; Skinner, D.; Ceder, G.; Persson, K. A. The Materials Project: A Materials Genome Approach to Accelerating Materials Innovation. *APL Materials* **2013**, *1* (1), 011002. DOI: 10.1063/1.4812323
30. Kresse, G.; Hafner, J. Ab Initio Molecular Dynamics For Liquid Metals. *Phys. Rev. B Condens Matter.* **1993**, *47* (1), 558-561. DOI: 10.1103/physrevb.47.558
31. Kresse, G.; Hafner, J. Ab Initio Molecular-Dynamics Simulation of the Liquid-Metal-Amorphous-Semiconductor Transition in Germanium. *Phys. Rev. B Condens Matter.* **1994**, *49* (20), 14251-14269. DOI: 10.1103/physrevb.49.14251
32. Kresse, G.; Furthmüller, J. Efficiency of Ab-initio Total Energy Calculations for Metals and Semiconductors Using a Plane-Wave Basis Set., *Comput. Mater. Sci.* **1996**, *6* (1), 15-50. DOI: 10.1016/0927-0256(96)00008-0

-
33. Kresse, G.; Furthmüller, J. Efficient Iterative Schemes for ab Initio Total-Energy Calculations Using a Plane-Wave Basis Set. *Phys. Rev. B Condens Matter*. **1996**, *54* (16), 11169-11186. DOI: 10.1103/PhysRevB.54.11169
34. Hammer, B.; Hansen, L. B.; Nørskov, J. K. Improved Adsorption Energetics within Density-Functional Theory Using Revised Perdew-Burke-Ernzerhof Functionals. *Phys. Rev. B* **1999**, *59* (11), 7413–7421. DOI: 10.1103/PhysRevB.59.7413
35. Blochl, P. E. Projector Augmented-Wave Method. *Phys. Rev. B Condens Matter*. **1994**, *50* (24), 17953-17979. DOI: 10.1103/PhysRevB.50.17953
36. Grimme, S. Semiempirical GGA-Type Density Functional Constructed with a Long-Range Dispersion Correction. *J. Comput. Chem.* **2006**, *27* (15), 1787-1799. DOI: 10.1002/jcc.20495
37. Grimme, S.; Antony, J.; Ehrlich, S.; Krieg, S. A Consistent and Accurate Ab Initio Parametrization of Density Functional Dispersion Correction (DFT-D) for the 94 elements H-Pu. *J. Chem. Phys.* **2010**, *132* (15), 154104. DOI: 10.1063/1.3382344
38. Jain, A.; Ong S. P.; Hautier, G.; Chen, W.; Richards, W. D.; Dacek, S.; Cholia, S.; Gunter, D.; Skinner, D.; Ceder, G.; Persson, K. A. The Materials Project: A Materials Genome Approach to Accelerating Materials Innovation. *APL Mater.* **2013**, *1*, 011002. DOI: 10.1063/1.4812323
39. Naito, K.; Nakamura, M; Sakata, O.; Hoshi, N. Surface X-ray Scattering of Pd(111) and Pd(100) Electrodes during the Oxygen Reduction Reaction. *Electrochemistry* **2011**, *79* , 256-260. DOI: 10.5796/ELECTROCHEMISTRY.79.256
40. Hoshi, N.; Noma, M.; Suzuki, T.; Hori, Y. Structural Effect on the Rate of CO₂ Reduction on Single Crystal Electrodes of Palladium. *J. Electroanal. Chem.* **1997**, *421* (1-2), 15-18. DOI: 10.1016/S0022-0728(96)01023-6
41. Ojha, K.; Doblhoff-Dier, K.; Koper, M.T.M. Double-layer structure of the Pt(111)–aqueous electrolyte interface. *Proc. Nat. Academy of Sci. USA* **2022**, *119*(3), e2116016119. DOI: 10.1073/pnas.2116016119

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42. Calle-Vallejo, F.; Martínez, J. I.; García-Lastra, J. M.; Sautet, P.; Loffreda, D. Fast Prediction of Adsorption Properties for Platinum Nanocatalysts with Generalized Coordination Numbers. *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.* **2014**, *53* (32), 8316-8319. DOI: 10.1002/anie.201402958
43. Calle-Vallejo, F.; Tymoczko, J.; Colic, V.; Vu, Q. H.; Pohl, M. D.; Morgenstern, K.; Loffreda, D.; Sautet, P.; Schuhmann, W.; Bandarenka A. S. Finding Optimal Surface Sites on Heterogeneous Catalysts by Counting Nearest Neighbors. *Science* **2015**, *350* (6257), 185-189. DOI: 10.1126/science.aab3501
44. Calle-Vallejo, F.; Bandarenka, A. S. Enabling Generalized Coordination Numbers to Describe Strain Effects. *ChemSusChem* **2018**, *11* (11), 1824-1828. DOI: 10.1002/cssc.201800569